

**VASUDHAIVA KUTUMBAKAM AND THE INNER REVOLUTION:
A PHILOSOPHICAL INQUIRY INTO EDUCATION THROUGH
KRISHNAMURTI'S AND OSHO'S VISION**

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Abstract

The ancient Indian axiom Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam – ‘the world is one family’ - has resurfaced as a global ideal resounding across ethical, legal, and sustainable arenas of contemporary life; be it the UN Peacekeeping conclave or the spirit behind India’s ‘vaccine maitri’ initiative during COVID-19 pandemic. Within education, this vision finds overwhelming importance in India’s National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, which stresses upon holistic development, equity and inclusion, global citizenship, and value-based learning. It strives to develop creative, ethical, technologically skilled, and environmentally conscious individuals. This paper explores how the educational philosophies of J. Krishnamurti and Osho propound transformative visions to realize the vision of Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam by way of an inward revolution of consciousness rather than through external systems alone. Both envision education as a process of psycho-spiritual awakening brought about by a balanced development of scientific thinking and meditative awareness, reason and love, intellect and intuition in individuals. Assuming that the meeting point of ethics, legality, and sustainability is education, this paper argues that education must cultivate awareness, compassion, and creativity which are the genuine foundations of global citizenship to realise the ideal of ‘one earth one family.’

Key words: NEP, J. Krishnamurti, Osho, awareness, education, compassion, awareness, balance.

Introduction

Education is the cornerstone of a society. Its approach and content shape generations and affect civilizations. Education therefore must be holistic, all-embracing and aim at evoking intelligence and freedom. This age is marked by reckless technological acceleration, alarming climate crises, and moral disintegration and calls for a shared holistic vision for humanity that is sensitive towards and inclusive of all. The concept of *Vasudhaiva*

Kutumbakam, found in the *Mahopanishad*, declares that all living beings on Earth form one interdependent family. In recent times this principle has re-emerged on international platforms. For instance, it was adopted as India's theme for the G20 Summit 2023 promoting integration and multilateralism. In the United Nations it has been used as the basis for promoting human rights and has also reflected in India's 'vaccine maitri' initiative during COVID-19 pandemic. The principle provides a unifying ethical and cultural basis for tackling global challenges through exchange of ideas, cooperation and mutual understanding. Education being the foundation of the perpetual reformation of any civilization, is central to the implementation of the ideal of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 envisions education as a means of creating responsible, ethical, and globally conscious citizens who embody human values, empathy and mindfulness towards environment. For such a transformation to be realistic, it must go beyond policy frameworks alone and reach the very core of educators and learners.

Jiddu Krishnamurti (1895 – 1986) and Osho (1931 – 1990) offer their vision on education exactly for this inner foundation to be evoked in educators and learners. Both thinkers offer a critique of the prevailing education and advocate the fundamental reawakening of awareness, freedom, and love as the true goals of learning. They challenge the utilitarian aims of modern education arguing that it creates conditioned, competitive and fragmented human being. Their insights offer the spiritual depth necessary to complement the ethical and educational dimensions of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*.

Rationale of the Study

While the concept of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam* is gaining popularity on national and international forums, its realisation may remain metaphorical unless it is evoked in the consciousness of individuals. Education has always been the driving force behind any social or cultural change. However, prevalent education rooted largely in competition, ambition, certification, and excessive technological dependence often isolate learners from themselves, nature and the real world. Education must facilitate lived experiences of challenges and conflict resolution through creative outlook deepening trust in interdependence and oneness of all.

This paper tries to fill this conceptual gap by investigating how Krishnamurti's and Osho's vision on education exemplify the inner transformation much required to establish the ideal of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*. By associating their insights to the pedagogical directions of NEP 2020, this paper presents a framework for re-envisaging education as the moral and

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spiritual foundation of the 'One Earth, One Family' model.

Objectives

To explore the educational principles underlying *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*.

To interpret Krishnamurti's and Osho's educational philosophies as pathways to internalizing global values.

To propose an educational model rooted in awareness, creativity, and compassion.

Research Methodology

The methodology of the research is reflective and synthesising, aiming to build theoretical coherence rather than empirical justification. The paper engages in a qualitative philosophical analysis based on interpretive and comparative methods. It integrates primary philosophical concepts from Krishnamurti's and Osho's writings with secondary literature on NEP 2020. Krishnamurti's and Osho's writings are interpreted in an elucidative manner to obtain educational principles applicable to the relevant discussion.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of this paper is philosophical and educational. It focuses on educational and ethical aspects rather than experimental or empirical case studies. The limitations of the study is that it adopts a non-quantitative approach and relies on interpretive analysis alone which is subjective. However, its merit lies in aligning ancient Indian ideals with modern educational frameworks for global interests.

Main Discussion:

The Ethical and Spiritual Implications of Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam

The vision 'the world is one family' is not a utopian ideal but a deep ontological insight into the interconnectedness and oneness of life. It is rooted in the Upanishadic declaration '*Sarvam Khalvidam Brahman*' which means 'All this, indeed, is Brahman.' It suggests that systems whether socio-political, ethical or educational, must evolve from the acknowledgement of shared existence. Equity, inclusiveness and sustainability, then, are not restricted to narrow management of human or environmental resources, but rather a veneration for the unity of all beings.

Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam envisions a global family and provides the basis for a universal ethical structure. It inspires universal brotherhood / sisterhood and an outlook that transcends national, racial and economic boundaries. It implicates shared responsibility, inherent respect for all life forms, empathy and cooperation towards all and moving beyond mere tolerance to celebrating diversity. The ethical basis of 'one world, one family' are compassion, justice and

truth. These high ideals call for an education that integrates ethical literacy with spiritual awareness at its core (Ranjalkar, 2025, chapter 14).

Highlights of NEP 2020 in Brief

The paradigm shift in the National Education Policy 2020 is its stress on holistic, multidisciplinary, value-based, and inclusive education. It envisions learners as global citizens entrenched in Indian values yet open to universal human affairs. The policy promotes ethical thinking, critical reasoning, problem solving and environmental awareness as essential competencies for the present era. Among its other recommendations, teacher empowerment, technology-enabled learning, and universal access to education for all are indeed significant. The policy in particular promotes Indian knowledge system to provide unique viewpoint on contemporary issues. (Swargiary, 2025, p. 124-144).

In the larger backdrop of the philosophy of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*, NEP 2020 can be seen as an endeavor to strike an equilibrium between globalization and cultural rootedness. Its focus on multidisciplinary education and experiential learning is in sync with the preposition that true education is holistic and self-illuminating; not constricted merely to employment generation and academic accreditation. However, implementing this vision requires a radical shift in perspective. Krishnamurti and Osho provide significant insights into bringing about internal transformation to consequently achieve an external reform. Their vision on education nudges humans towards true critical thinking and attaining holistic development rooted in awareness, love and authenticity which are indispensable to promote the spirit of ‘one world one family.’

Krishnamurti’s Vision of Education

Krishnamurti advocates a holistic education directed towards nurturing integrated, intelligent and creative humans. For him, education implies questioning and enquiring all phenomena. It is not mere accumulation of information and knowledge but rather freeing the mind from psychological conditioning and producing clarity. Through questioning the learners must be encouraged to unburden themselves from various forms of conditioning that lead to ambition, fear, slavery, and conformity. The aim of education according to Krishnamurti is to prepare the learner to be able to face the idiosyncrasies of the world and not succumb to them. The learner must become capable of love, compassion and freedom and not be straightjacketed to fit to the norms of the society. Thus, education must become an inquiry into oneself and into the structure of thought itself. He emphasised the need for a child-centred and co-operation based learning as opposed to a competitive and educator-centric

system. He insisted that the teachers should be wise, fearless and inspiring. These principles reflect in the NEP wherein due stress is given on student-centric learning and upscaling the efficiencies of the teachers (Krishnamurti, 1992, p. 23-25, 41,42, 103-123).

Krishnamurti's insistence on developing choice-less awareness is in sync with the ethical spirit of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*. The impartial witnessing of thoughts and inner states dissolves the egoic self to a larger extent and one starts becoming aware of the false divide between individuals, groups, races, nations, etc. In such awareness, all-embracing love becomes possible. His vision of education rejects authority-based systems and advocates dialogue, observation, and freedom. Krishnamurti schools such as Rishi Valley and Brockwood Park, exemplify this approach by assimilating observation of nature, sitting in silence, and encouraging inquiry into learning. Such prototypes demonstrate how education can foster global citizens embodying compassion and empathy rather than ideology (Jayakar, 1986, p. 190-193).

Osho's Vision of Education

Osho, like Krishnamurti, saw education as a process of awakening - fostering intelligence, love, creativity and meditateness. He insists that education should promote cooperation and not competition among learners. Holistic education according to him implies the development of both - intellect and the heart (emotional intelligence/empathy). The purpose of education is to draw from within the individual the spirit of honesty, love and truthfulness. The approach is to help individuals free themselves from the constraints of imposed beliefs and ideologies and not take recourse to disciplined imposition of values through negative or positive reinforcement. For Osho, holistic human growth depends on balancing critical thinking and meditation, intellect and intuition, reason and compassion. He envisaged an education that synchronizes the outer and inner aspects of life - producing not scholars or sages alone, but whole human beings. Osho criticised modern education for promoting ambition, competition and alienation from real life. According to him conventional education based on reward and punishment represses in the young learners natural intelligence, spontaneity, and creativity. He proposed meditation as the foundation of learning. When pupils learn to be silent, there is a possibility to re-discover spontaneity, love, and truthfulness. Such inner balance and tranquillity, according to Osho, is the beginning of a sustainable and peaceful world (Osho, 2006, p. 75-97, 105-112, 164-176).

Much like the concept of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*, Osho's concept of family transcends humanity to embrace all life. According to Osho, sustainable growth is possible only through

a profound inner shift in humans from the state of greed to one of love for cosmos and creativity. In sync with the spirit of NEP 2020, Osho supports the use of ‘super technology’ to tackle modern day challenges. However, without spiritual transformation technological development is futile, he emphatically asserts.

Converging Principles Toward a Sustainable, Humanistic Education

Osho and Krishnamurti envision an education that attempts unravelling nothing less than existence itself; body, mind, emotion, creativity, spirituality, life and death. They differ on subjects like meditation and art but have mutual agreement on the objective of education, role of educators (parents and teachers) and an emphasis on the creation of right environment for evoking the spirit of inquiry in learners rather than imposition of knowledge. Both hold modern education responsible for partial and lopsided development of human and a production of mediocre populace which is in the service and domination of existing decaying social norms and values.

Insights on education by Osho and Krishnamurti have undoubtedly made a mark on the intelligentsia of recent times, the light of which can be seen in changing trends in education: altered syllabus and curriculums, attempts to replace marking system with grading system, introduction of environmental studies, etc. However a policy encouraging inner transformation is still anticipated. The educators and the makers of the system if devoid of love and self-knowledge can find it testing to transform a deteriorating system.

Krishnamurti and Osho hold the spirit of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam* by advocating self-realisation as the central objective of education. Self-realization they hold is the realization of oneness of existence – ‘you are the world.’ This can be brought about by imparting individuals inner observation, ethical sensitivity and all-embracing empathy. Meditation and awareness are the tools to achieve this goal according to Osho and Krishnamurti. They recommend holistic development of the body, mind and spirit and establishing intimate connectivity with nature because the well-being of the planet and humans is inseparable. Both envision an education that frees mind from fear and imitation and aim at nurturing learners who are intelligent, creative, co-operative and loving. Such empathetic, creative individuals alone can strive to attain ‘one world, one family’, they would agree (Krishnamurti, 2002, p. 143-145; Osho, 2005, p. 7, 23-25).

Conclusion

The ageless insight of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam* finds revived importance in an antagonistic and divided world searching for unity. Its ethical, legal, and sustainable precepts meet in the

dominion of education, where the seeds of love, empathy and understanding are sown. The vision of Krishnamurti and Osho enlightens the path towards an education that transcends boundaries and fosters the inner harmony essential for global peace.

Incorporating their insights into the NEP 2020 framework could deepen the policy's transformative potential. Beyond skills and employability, education must foster awareness, silence, and love as the true means of realizing the 'one earth, one family' vision.

Recommendations

1. **Incorporate Silent Sitting Practices:** Meditation and/or silent sitting sessions should be incorporated in school and university curricula.
2. **Redefine Success:** Focus should be moved from competition to co-operation. Learners should not be tagged as 'successful' or 'failure'; instead they must be encouraged to deepen interest in a subject of their choice, take alternate ways to approach it or change subjects of interest voluntarily.
3. **Teacher Training in Holistic Pedagogy:** Educators should be trained to encourage enquiry rather than impose conformity.
4. **Nurturing Environmental and Ethical consciousness:** Sustainability must be taught on the basis of love and non-violence towards all sentients and not as a caution or warning against an impending disaster.
5. **Institutional Reform:** Educational institutions should adopt democratic policies towards both educators and learners and grant them autonomy, time and space to facilitate a culture of dialogue, investigation, concern, creativity and socio-environmental sensitivity aligned with the essence of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*.

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